

Deep Vision for Automated Quality Assessment and Adulteration Detection of Rice Grains

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Abstract— Rice is a fundamental element of sustenance in India, serving as a staple for a vast majority of the population. Hence, ensuring the quality of rice grains becomes imperative to meet consumer expectations and uphold food safety and public health. However, traditional quality grading methods have proven to be labour-intensive and prone to errors and inefficiencies. In light of these limitations, this paper proposes a computer vision solution, employing the state-of-the-art YOLOv8 object detection model in a web application. By deploying a YOLOv8 model trained on a meticulously annotated dataset, the system adeptly detects and categorizes rice grains based on quality-indicative, key physical characteristics such as chalkiness, wholeness, damage/discoloration, and presence of foreign particles. Further, the paper proposes a solution to identify potential varietal adulteration of rice grains by applying contour extraction on the images. Through this endeavour, the paper highlights the transformative potential of deep vision technology in automating rice quality assessment, thereby offering a pragmatic solution applicable across agricultural and food industry domains.

Keywords— Computer Vision, Contour Extraction, Deep Vision, Machine Learning, Object Detection, Rice Quality, YOLOv8

I. INTRODUCTION

Food grains have exhibited profound significance in India's culinary history and heritage, forming the basis of sustenance that has influenced the nation's dietary traditions [20][21]. Among these grains, rice, notably, carries great importance. Concerns regarding the quality of rice grains that are being distributed and consumed are becoming more pressing. The widespread adulteration of these grains presents a significant threat to food integrity, compounded by environmental factors such as shifting climate patterns affecting rice cultivation conditions. Suboptimal storage practices further compromise rice quality, resulting in a gradual loss of nutritional value. Unforeseen circumstances such as natural disasters or transportation disruptions exacerbate challenges in the journey from farm to table.

The consequences of these challenges are significant, negatively impacting the nutritional value of rice grains and imposing a considerable burden on the health and livelihoods of those reliant on them. In this dynamic environment, advancements in automation and computer vision emerge as promising solutions, heralding a new era of innovation poised to tackle these urgent issues. Beyond just mitigating human error, automation has the potential to enhance efficiency, scalability, and the overall quality of grain and food assessments.

This paper introduces a solution that contributes to the domain of rice grain quality assessment. Section II of this paper provides a summary of recent advancements and related work in the field of food quality assessment and related domains. In Section III, we detail the comprehensive methodology encompassing manual acquisition and annotation of images, followed by model training and deployment within a web application framework in Section IV. To establish the classification criteria for rice grains, we conducted a thorough analysis of quality-indicative visual characteristics. These traits were meticulously examined and narrowed down to four key categories – 1) Chalkiness - This refers to the milky appearance of rice grains caused by irregular starch granules or air pockets. Chalkiness diminishes the cooking quality of rice, making it less desirable for consumption. The presence of chalkiness has been attributed to various factors such as high temperatures and stress due to heat [9]. On the whole, a higher percentage of such grains in a sample is indicative of poor or substandard quality; 2) Wholeness - Wholeness signifies the intactness of rice grains, reflecting their resilience to damage.; 3) Discoloration/Damage - Discoloration and damage indicate blemishes or irregularities on rice grains, often resulting from moisture, pests, or mechanical factors. Such imperfections may indicate potential spoilage or mishandling; 4) Presence of Impurities - Impurities encompass any foreign particles or contaminants present in rice grains, posing health risks and diminishing the purity of the product. We have focused on 2 impurities found in rice – plastic and stone. Further, we have trained the DNN model to also recognize other foreign particles (excluding plastic and stone) under a general class. These key features can be visually detected. Throughout the training process, the model familiarizes itself with patterns and characteristics linked to the quality traits while scrutinizing spatial relationships. For example, chalky rice exhibits a noticeably more whitish or opaque appearance compared to non-chalky varieties.

Preserving the integrity of rice in terms of its variety is essential to uphold quality standards and guarantee that consumers receive the precise type of rice they anticipate. Regrettably, adulteration poses a threat to authenticity, potentially undermining the purity of rice products. Section III also details a solution to identify varietal adulteration in rice grains by employing an area-based approach. The goal of this project is to create a software tool that accurately detects and classifies rice grains in images/videos using predefined quality traits. We strive to develop an efficient solution that improves the rice grain quality grading process.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

This section provides an overview of recent progress and studies primarily focused on automated analysis of grain quality. Expanding beyond grains, the review encompasses a range of sectors, including the detection of unwanted components in soft foods and the evaluation of apple ripeness, among other applications. The main goal is to gain a comprehensive understanding of methodologies, challenges, and technological advancements across various food products and agricultural fields. By exploring the methodologies and limitations of each study, this review aims to offer insights into emerging technological trends, facilitating a deeper understanding of the current landscape and promoting further research in the field. Table 1 summarizes recent related work.

TABLE I
SUMMARIZED WORKS

Sl No.	Title	Journal	Methodology	Outcome	Limitations/ Future Scope
[1]	An annotated grain kernel image database for visual quality inspection	IEEE November 2023	A machine vision database comprising 350,000+ grain kernel images from wheat, maize, sorghum, and rice was developed. Utilizing high-resolution optic sensors and expert annotations, detailed grain information was gathered. Deep CNNs, pretrained on ImageNet, were fine-tuned on PyTorch with GPU acceleration, employing data augmentations and CrossEntropy loss optimization.	ResNet-152 and other deep learning models outperformed traditional methods, achieving high F1-scores: 99.9% for wheat, 97.2% for maize, 96.8% for sorghum, and 94.1% for rice. Visualization techniques confirmed dataset quality by distinguishing normal from damaged grains.	—
[2]	Machine Learning Analysis of Hyperspectral Images of Damaged Wheat Kernels	MDPI March 2023	Hyperspectral Imaging (HSI) was done to evaluate the damage done by the fungus <i>Fusarium graminearum</i> in wheat kernels. Machine Learning models were evaluated to ascertain which of them was more accurate.	G-Boost was found to perform the best with an accuracy of 97% in classifying wheat kernels into different severity levels.	The research employed images capturing only one side of the kernels. Enhancing model performance could be achieved by scanning both sides.
[3]	Application of Machine Learning for Insect Monitoring in Grain Facilities	MDPI March 2023	A system for insect detection was created, employing a manual-focus camera and a Jetson Nano running a trained deep-learning model. The model utilizes live video feed to identify small insects.	An accuracy of 70-85% was obtained using side-by-side comparison.	Integration of cloud services could enhance data storage and retrieval could be implemented. Development of a mobile platform with processing and communication abilities could enable data transmission to a server for further

					processing and user feedback
[4]	Study on Rice Grain Mildewed Region Recognition Based on Microscopic Computer Vision and YOLO-v5 Model	MDPI December 2022	Three YOLO-v5 models, for each mould variety, were built for recognizing regions of mildew in microscopic mouldy rice grain images.	Accuracy of identification of each of the mildewed regions with contamination of <i>A. niger</i> , <i>P. citrinum</i> , and <i>A.</i> were found to be 89.26%, 91.15%, and 90.19%, respectively.	The proposed system detects moldy regions on individual rice grains and suggests the potential for developing recognition models for grouped rice samples via transfer learning. Expanding detection capabilities to include other types of mold requires obtaining a more extensive collection of mildew rice grains.
[5]	Fast and accurate wheat grain quality detection based on improved YOLOv5	Elsevier November 2022	Wheat quality detection was achieved by enhancing YOLOv5 with sparse network pruning and a hybrid attenuation module to mitigate degradation concerns.	A benchmark wheat grain dataset has been constructed. The proposed model was found to perform with an accuracy of 97%.	Future research could focus on enhancing performance by combining the speed of visible image acquisition devices with the precision of hyperspectral image acquisition devices.
[6]	Vision-Based Defect Classification and Weight Estimation of Rice Kernels	IEEE November 2022	The proposed system evaluated rice kernel quality and categorized grains based on their defects, utilizing a pixel area-based metric to calculate weight ratios of kernels in the image. A multi-stage workflow was devised for the classification of kernel flaws.	The model exhibited a precision of over 85% for recognition of all six kernel flaws and a precision of over 90% for sound, broken, yellow-coloured and spotted kernels.	Research into methods for reducing the demands on training data quantity and quality is recommended. Improving the network model's adaptability to professionally labeled data is crucial, given the challenges in data acquisition.
[7]	Apple Fruit Quality Detector Using Fiber Optics and Color Sensor	IEEE November 2022	A portable system, consisting of a colour sensor and optical fiber has been proposed, that takes into account the amount of light reflected from apples to determine their mellowness.	The system was found to detect ripeness with an accuracy of 97%	Future research could involve expanding the application of the proposed system to detect the ripeness of different types of fruits. Focus could be placed on

					improving performance to achieve a 100% accuracy rate.
[8]	Computer-Assisted Real-Time Rice Variety Learning Using Deep Learning Network	Elsevier September 2022	An automated rice grading system was developed using the AlexNet architecture. Real-time processing was enabled through the utilization of a NI-myRIO equipped with a high-resolution camera and user interface.	Using AlexNet architecture, an average accuracy of 98.2% with 97.6% sensitivity and 96.4% specificity was obtained.	–
[9]	Deep learning based high-throughput phenotyping of chalkiness in rice exposed to high night temperature.	BMC January 2022	Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and Gradient-weighted Class Activation Mapping (Grad-CAM) were used to detect chalkiness in rice grain images.	The tested Grad-CAM model with a ResNet-101 backbone can be used to accurately detect chalkiness in images of rice grains. Detection was found to be easier in polished rice compared to unpolished rice.	The system's limitations include its applicability only to white rice, ineffective transferability of models from polished to unpolished rice, and lack of assessment for chalkiness without physical grain separation. Further training is needed for accurate quantification, especially with grain overlap.
[10]	Detection of Wheat Unsound Kernels Based on Improved ResNet	IEEE January 2022	Various ResNet models were improved and enhanced to detect unsound wheat kernels from wheat grains images.	The Res24_D_CBAM_Atrous model was found to perform the best with an accuracy of 94%.	Future work could automate testing equipment, ensure stable image acquisition scenes, and develop a robust dataset for unsound kernels to improve standardization. Establishing a detection standard for the unsound kernel rate based on mass ratio could also be beneficial.
[11]	Detection of Foreign Bodies in Soft Foods Employing Tactile Image Sensor	Frontiers December 2021	Cylindrical tactile image sensor was used to detect shell fragments left on the surface of raw shrimp and bones left in fish fillets.	Tactile image sensor was used to successfully detect hard objects in three types of soft food.	The system's applicability extends to various food items in real-world scenarios. Although successful in detecting shells on the front side of shrimp, those on the back remain undetected.

					Optimal foreign matter detection required force variation between 2 to 7 N. Future enhancements could involve adding a mechanism to maintain a constant force, ensuring consistent inspection conditions.
[12]	Computer Vision and Machine Learning Analysis of Commercial Rice Grains: A Potential Digital Approach for Consumer Perception Studies	MDPI September 2021	An Artificial Neural Network (ANN) model was developed using nine morpho-colorimetric parameters to classify the rice samples into 15 commercial rice types.	The Bayesian Regularization (BR) algorithm of the ANN with ten hidden neurons achieved the highest classification accuracy. Training accuracy was 91.6% (MSE < 0.01), testing accuracy was 88.5% (MSE = 0.01), resulting in an overall accuracy of 90.7%. Deployment accuracy for rice sample classification was 93.9%.	Connections could be established between the readily accessible parameters with key traits in rice. The proposed method can be applied in the industry to develop a cloud-based smartphone application for real-time assessment of rice quality.
[13]	Safety of Food and Food Warehouse Using VIBHISHAN	Hindawi September 2021	An automated robot, VIBHISHAN, was built to ensure warehouse safety as well as to identify the food conditions. A machine learning model for detecting the food was developed by using CNN. After training.	The CNN based model exhibited an accuracy of 96.30%	–
[14]	High-throughput soybean seeds phenotyping with convolutional neural networks and transfer learning	BMC May 2021	A hybrid simulated/real dataset for training and evaluation of high throughput soybean seeds was developed. The synthetic image dataset was used for transfer learning with Mask R-CNN to perform high throughput instance segmentation of soybean seeds.	The proposed method for synthetic image generation and augmentation and the use of transfer learning methods achieved the objective of automated soybean seeds phenotyping.	The suggested system utilized 2D images, lacking depth analysis. Improvements are needed to reduce the computational cost of training the segmentation model. Expanding the synthetic image generation and augmentation technique to include multiple classes could enhance the methodology.

[15]	Identification of Rice Varieties and Adulteration Using Gas Chromatography-Ion Mobility Spectrometry	IEEE January 2021	<p>Headspace-gas chromatography-ion mobility spectrometry (HGC-IMS) was employed to analyze volatile compounds in five types of rice.</p> <p>A semi-supervised generative adversarial network (SSGAN) was applied to identify unique ion migration fingerprints for these rice types, enabling accurate classification of HGC-IMS images.</p>	The proposed model was found to exhibit 98% accuracy in recognizing the rice types and 97.30% in recognizing adulteration in rice.	The proposed method could be applied to identify food crops apart from rice.
[16]	Analysis and Identification of Rice Adulteration Using Terahertz Spectroscopy and Pattern Recognition Algorithms	IEEE January 2020	Terahertz spectroscopy and pattern recognition algorithms were utilized to detect and analyze adulterated rice across five levels with varying mixing proportions. Principle Component Analysis (PCA) was employed for feature extraction.	The support vector machine (SVM) model, utilizing absorption spectra with first derivative pretreatment, achieved an accuracy of 97.33%.	The research was constrained to high-quality, low-cost rice. Enhancements in the study could involve considering additional rice varieties to create a more effective and realistic system.

III. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

In this section we will first introduce the methodology employed to train the DNN model to detect and classify RoIs into the 8 classes specified. The results from the trained model are then used to detect potential varietal adulteration.

A. Model Training

Analysis of key, quality-indicative physical characteristics of rice grains resulted in the solidification of the classes that the model would learn to classify rice grains into. These classes are – 1) ‘sound’ - Grains that do not present any defects are classified as ‘sound’; 2) ‘whole-chalky’ – Whole (i.e, unbroken), chalky rice grains fall under this category; 3) ‘broken-clear’ – Broken, non-chalky rice grains are classified as ‘broken-clear’; 4) ‘broken-chalky’ – Grains that are broken and chalky as classified under this class; 5) ‘unsound’ – A slightly broader category, encapsulating discoloured and damaged rice grains; 6) ‘plastic’ – Presence of plastic in rice is a health hazard. Hence the model was trained to identify pieces of plastic in a sample of rice; 7) ‘stone’ – The presence of stones in rice is indicative of improper handling and cleaning of rice; 8) ‘foreign-object’ – A more general class to identify foreign objects apart from stone and plastic.

Fig. 1 System Design

Fig. 1 depicts the system design and workflow, including the process of training a model and obtaining weights.

1) Acquisition of Images

A representative collection of images is essential for effectively training a robust object detection model and facilitating its ability to generalize effectively. One key issue faced during the development of this system was the unavailability of a well annotated dataset to train the model on. Hence, the first step in building the system was to generate a dataset. The images of rice grains were captured using a smartphone camera. 144 images were captured manually.

2) Pre-Processing

Before model training, a series of pre-processing steps are undertaken to standardize the images. This involves ensuring uniform image resolution, format, and colour to maintain consistency. Additionally, image enhancement techniques are applied to improve clarity and accentuate important grain features, preparing the dataset for effective model learning.

3) Dataset Creation

The proposed solution is an object detection task. Object detection involves training a model to identify regions of interest (RoIs) within an image and classify them by drawing bounding boxes around the detected objects. In order to train an object detection model (such as YOLO), the dataset must consist of images which have been annotated with bounding boxes around the target objects. Hence, once the images were acquired, manual annotation of images was performed by drawing bounding boxes around the grains and assigning a class label to each grain, distinguishing between the categories. This task was done using Roboflow's annotation tool.

To facilitate robust model evaluation, the dataset is strategically split into training, validation and testing sets in an 80:10:10 ratio. In order to increase the size of the dataset and to ensure that the model generalises well to unseen data, data augmentation was done to artificially increase the number of images in the training set. Post augmentation, the dataset consisted of 371 images.

4) YOLOv8 Training

The YOLO (You Only Look Once) algorithm is a state-of-the-art object detection model in computer vision. Unlike conventional approaches, it reframes object detection as a regression task. It partitions an image into a grid and forecasts bounding boxes along with class probabilities for each grid cell. YOLO directly anticipates bounding box positions and links them with class probabilities, facilitating rapid processing in real-time. Fig. 2[18] shows the basic steps involved in any YOLO model.

Fig. 2 Steps followed by YOLO model

YOLOv8 employs a convolutional neural network divided into two main components: the backbone and the head. The YOLOv8 architecture is depicted in Fig. 3.[24]

Fig. 3 YOLOv8 Architecture

a) *Backbone Architecture:*

The core structure of YOLOv8 is constructed on a customized iteration of CSPDarknet53 as its backbone architecture. This configuration consists of 53 convolutional layers and integrates cross-stage partial connections. These cross-stage partial connections are instrumental in improving the exchange of information across various layers, thereby facilitating effective feature extraction and enhancing the learning of representations within the neural network.

b) *Head Architecture:*

The head of YOLOv8 incorporates several convolutional layers followed by a sequence of fully connected layers. This segment of the architecture is pivotal in the prediction phase, responsible for establishing bounding boxes, objectness scores, and class probabilities for identified objects. The organization of these layers significantly influences the model's capability to precisely detect and classify objects within an image.

c) *Self-Attention Mechanism:*

A notable advancement in YOLOv8 is the integration of a self-attention mechanism within the head of the network. This feature empowers the model to dynamically prioritize different areas of the image, modulating the significance of various features according to their relevance in object detection. By doing so, the self-attention mechanism boosts the model's flexibility in handling a wide array of visual patterns and complexities.

d) *Multi-Scaled Object Detection:*

YOLOv8 demonstrates exceptional performance in multi-scaled object detection by integrating a feature pyramid network. Tailored to detect objects across different sizes and scales within an image, this network encompasses multiple layers. Consequently, YOLOv8 is proficient in identifying both large and small objects with precision. This versatility renders YOLOv8 well-suited for a diverse array of object detection scenarios.

The YOLOv8 architecture is employed for training on the annotated dataset. Configuring hyperparameters, including the learning rate and batch size, is crucial to optimizing the model's convergence during training.

5) Performance Evaluation

Model performance is rigorously evaluated using the validation set and metrics such as Mean Average Precision (mAP), Precision and Recall. The evaluation results guide the fine-tuning of the model, aiming to improve accuracy and ensure strong generalization to diverse conditions.

The trained YOLOv8 model is deployed to classify rice grains in real-world images. The model's accuracy in identifying grain quality classes is evaluated across various conditions. This step marks the practical application of the trained model in real-world scenarios for grain quality assessment.

In practical scenarios, the challenge often involves assessing the quality of an entire bag of grains. Current quality checkpoints address this by sampling grains from various sections of the bag for quality detection. Employing a similar strategy, images of grains from diverse areas of the bag can be captured to derive the average quality of the entire grain batch.

B. Detection of Varietal Adulteration

Varietal adulteration in rice grains denotes the fraudulent practice of blending different rice varieties or substituting inferior rice types for higher-quality ones. This deceit undermines the genuineness and integrity of the rice product, potentially resulting in inconsistencies in quality, flavour, and nutritional content.

Algorithm 1 walks through the procedure we have used to identify if the sample of rice grains exhibits this form of adulteration.

Algorithm 1: Detection of Varietal Adulteration in Rice Grains

Input:

Image: The input image containing rice grains

Results: Detection results obtained from trained YOLOv8 model

Output:

Conclusion: Indicates the presence and severity of varietal adulteration in the rice grains

Procedure:

1. Initialize an empty list to store the areas of detected rice grains (grainAreas).
2. Set Results = Filtered results for 'sound' and 'whole-chalky' from Results
3. Convert the input image to grayscale
4. For each detection result in Results:
 - a. Extract the coordinates (x_center, y_center, width, height) of the detected rice grain.
 - b. Calculate the region of interest (ROI) coordinates (x1, y1, x2, y2) based on the detected grain.

- ```

x1 = max(0, x_center - width // 2)
y1 = max(0, y_center - height // 2)
x2 = min(img_width, x_center + width // 2)
y2 = min(img_height, y_center + height // 2)

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- c. Extract the grain's region of interest from the grayscale image.
  - d. Preprocess the RoI by applying Gaussian blur and thresholding.
  - e. Find contours in the preprocessed RoI.
  - f. Calculate the area of each contour and store the maximum area in grainAreas.
4. Calculate the mean area (Mean) and standard deviation (S.D) of the rice grain areas.
  5. Compute the coefficient of variation (CoV) using the formula:  $\text{CoV} = (\text{S.D} / \text{Mean}) * 100$ .
  6. If  $\text{CoV} \geq 35$  and  $\text{CoV} < 45$ :
    - Set Conclusion as "Moderate adulteration detected".
  7. Else if  $\text{CoV} \geq 45$ :
    - Set Conclusion as "Severe adulteration detected".
  8. Else:
    - Set Conclusion as "No significant adulteration detected".
  9. Return Conclusion.

In the context of image processing, a contour is a curve joining continuous points along the boundary of an object with the same colour or intensity. For this use case, we have limited the contour extraction process to regions of interest classified as 'sound' and 'whole-chalky' by the trained YOLOv8 model. This decision was made due to the fact that it is easier to visually identify the variety of a single rice grain if it is intact/unbroken. Hence the first step is to filter out these classes from the model prediction results. The model results consist of a class identifier for each region detected and classified and the dimensions of the bounding box ( $x\_center$ ,  $y\_center$ , width, height). The co-ordinates of the bounding box in the image are calculated and used to crop areas of the input image, which has been converted to grayscale.

Further processing is done on these extracted areas. For each area (i.e, each result), Gaussian blur is applied to smooth the grayscale region of rice grains, reducing noise and creating a more uniform background, enhancing the visibility of grain boundaries. In the next step, thresholding is applied to the Gaussian-blurred image of rice grains. Thresholding involves converting the grayscale image into a binary image, where pixels are classified as either black or white based on their intensity values. We have applied inverse binary thresholding, which results in the rice grain regions being represented by black pixels and the background by white pixels, Otsu's thresholding method is used, which automatically calculates the optimal threshold value based on the image histogram to separate foreground (rice grains) from background.

Fig. 4 Examples of Extracted Contour Regions(filled)

Contours are identified from the binary image generated after thresholding, capturing continuous black regions representing rice grains. These contours are filled to obtain the complete grain regions. Fig. 4 depicts a few visualizations of such extracted regions. This method faces a challenge. Due to the non-uniform distribution of rice grains and existence of touching grains in real-world scenarios, each RoI can have more than one contour regions. Hence the maximum area among the identified contours is considered as the grain area. This approach compensates for overlapping grain regions within each region of interest (ROI).

The mean, standard deviation, and coefficient of variation are computed, from the list of all the areas obtained from the initial input image, providing insight into the uniformity of grain sizes within the image. A predefined threshold value of 35% is applied to the coefficient of variation: if it exceeds this threshold but remains below 45%, moderate varietal adulteration is inferred; if it equals or surpasses 45%, severe adulteration is concluded, based on research and experimentation.

#### IV. IMPLEMENTATION

Fig. 1 illustrates the operational design of the system, which is structured into three main stages: Dataset Creation, Model Training, and Inference in Streamlit. Section III detailed the processes involved in dataset creation and model training. Model training and performance evaluation are iterative, with the model being re-trained by adding more images to the dataset or fine-tuning hyperparameters until satisfactory results are achieved.

In our implementation, we leveraged the power of PyTorch, an open-source machine learning framework developed by Facebook's AI Research lab (FAIR). PyTorch offers a dynamic computational graph system that facilitates efficient model training and optimization through automatic differentiation. Our choice of PyTorch allowed us to seamlessly build, train, and evaluate the model for rice grain detection and classification. The trained YOLOv8 model's most effective weights were saved as 'best.pt', encapsulating the learned parameters essential for accurate inference tasks.

For deployment and creating an intuitive user interface, we turned to Streamlit, an open-source Python framework renowned for its simplicity and effectiveness in building interactive web applications. Streamlit enabled us to develop a user-friendly application where users can upload images, videos, or stream live video feeds for real-time analysis. The integration of our trained model with Streamlit facilitated seamless rice grain detection and classification, empowering users to interact with the model effortlessly.

In our application, users have the flexibility to upload images and compare the detected results with the original images using an intuitive image slider interface. Additionally, we incorporated descriptive bar charts to visualize the distribution of rice grains among various classes, providing users with valuable insights into the detected grains' characteristics.

Furthermore, we ensured compatibility with Real-Time Streaming Protocol (RTSP) feeds, allowing users to provide their camera or streaming channel's RTSP address for seamless real-time analysis. This capability broadens the application's scope, enabling users to analyze rice grain quality directly from live camera feeds or streaming channels, enhancing its versatility and practicality in real-world scenarios.

Moreover, our application extends its capabilities to support video uploads and RTSP livestreams, enabling the detection, classification, and individual tracking of rice grains within video footage. We employed ByteTrack, a sophisticated tracking system, to facilitate accurate grain tracking in videos and live feeds, enhancing the application's functionality and usability.

In addition to rice grain detection and classification, we employed OpenCV (Open-Source Computer Vision Library) to implement varietal adulteration detection within our application. OpenCV is a powerful open-source library that provides various tools and algorithms for computer vision tasks, including image processing, object detection, and contour analysis.

Our approach towards this problem involved preprocessing the input images, including Gaussian blurring to reduce noise and thresholding to segment rice grains from the background effectively. Subsequently, we applied contour extraction techniques provided by OpenCV to identify the boundaries of rice grains within the images. By calculating the areas of these contours, we obtained crucial information about the size and shape of individual rice grains, which served as the basis for further analysis.

Using statistical measures such as mean, standard deviation, and coefficient of variation computed from the grain areas, we quantified the variation in grain sizes within the images. This statistical analysis provided insights into the uniformity of rice grains, enabling us to detect varietal adulteration.

#### V. RESULTS

The trained model was evaluated primarily on the following evaluation metrics - mAP, Precision and Recall. mAP (mean Average Precision) is a measure of the overall performance of an object detection model. It calculates the average precision across all classes, considering both precision and recall. A higher mAP indicates better performance. The formula for mAP involves calculating the average precision for each class and then averaging them. Precision quantifies the proportion of accurately predicted positive observations relative to all predicted positive observations, reflecting the model's accuracy in positive predictions. Higher precision signifies fewer false positives.

$$Precision = \frac{True\ Positives}{True\ Positives + False\ Positives}$$

Recall, also known as sensitivity or true positive rate, measures the ratio of correctly predicted positive observations to the total actual positive observations. It represents the model's ability to identify all positive instances correctly. A greater recall value signifies a reduced occurrence of false negatives.

$$Recall = \frac{True\ Positives + False\ Positives}{True\ Positives}$$

The trained YOLOv8 model exhibits high performance, with a mean Average Precision (mAP) of 94%, Precision of 87.3%, and Recall of 88.2%. These elevated metrics affirm the model's adeptness in accurately detecting and classifying rice grains. Furthermore, Fig. 5 showcases the confusion matrix, a pivotal tool for evaluating the model's efficacy. The confusion matrix provides a detailed breakdown of true positives, true negatives, false positives, and false negatives, offering invaluable insights into the model's classification accuracy. It serves as a means for assessing the model's strengths and areas for refinement with precision and clarity.

Fig. 5 Confusion Matrix

Performance of the model can be visualized in the graphs depicted in Fig. 6.

Fig.6 Model Performance Graphs

The web application enables the user to choose between uploading a locally stored image, video or running inference on a live camera feed. These functionalities are displayed below.

Fig.7 Inference on Image

Fig.8 Inference on Video with Class Filters

Fig.9 Inference on Livestream

## VI. CONCLUSION

This paper presents a robust solution for automated rice grain quality assessment using computer vision techniques, specifically utilizing the YOLOv8 model. By meticulously curating a dataset, training the model, and deploying it via a Streamlit application, the system accurately detects and classifies rice grains into various categories as follows- sound, broken-clear, whole-chalky, broken-chalky, unsound, plastic, stone and foreign-object. Evaluation of the trained model demonstrates good performance metrics, including a mean Average Precision (mAP) of 94%, Precision of 87.3%, and Recall of 88.2%, affirming its reliability and accuracy. Furthermore, the integration of ByteTrack for individual grain tracking enhances the system's capabilities. The paper also introduces a simple yet effective approach for detecting varietal adulteration in rice grains, leveraging contour area detection techniques.

The authors have also conducted studies into various technologies being used in the food quality detection industry, more specifically in grain sorting and grading industry and have developed this project by keeping potential integration of the application with such technologies in mind. Overall, this research offers a comprehensive solution for automated rice grain quality assessment, showcasing its potential for real-world applications in the agriculture industry.

The paper highlights the significance of automation and computer vision in revolutionizing rice grain quality assessment, offering a practical solution for enhancing food quality and consumer satisfaction in the agricultural domain. The project was undertaken with the aim of advancing food quality assessment practices by addressing inefficiencies inherent in manual methods through the implementation of a machine learning solution. Additionally, this endeavor aims to stimulate ongoing exploration into the integration of automation within quality grading processes, paving the way for continued innovation in the field.

## VII. FUTURE ENHANCEMENTS

The system demonstrates high accuracy metrics and overall performance. Nonetheless, it possesses inherent limitations warranting further refinement.

Due to the limited availability of diverse samples, discolored and damaged rice grains have been consolidated under the 'unsound' class for simplicity. Future endeavors could involve defining a more granular classification and curating a representative dataset encapsulating all the defined classes in healthy proportions.

The model has been trained on 2D images and may lead to misclassifications of defective grains with obscured defects, particularly those situated away from the camera lens. While video inference capability exists, this functionality remains untested.

The solution proposed by this paper is focused on commercial white rice only. Future enhancements could include incorporating coloured rice varieties into the dataset and defining quality parameters for the same.

The methodology employed to detect varietal adulteration is a simple, yet effective one. However, this method would likely not be very effective when dealing with heavy occlusion and overlapping of grains. Future work could include developing a more robust solution to identify varietal adulteration.

To extend the project's applicability to real-world industrial settings, integration with industry-grade cameras and machinery is crucial. This necessitates a comprehensive understanding of specific factory or site requirements to develop tailored solutions catering to individual use cases.

The proposed methodology could be applied to detect the quality of other food grains or food products. This would require a thorough understanding of what parameters are indicative of quality of that product.

## ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

It has been proven time and again that behind good progress and accomplishment lies the right kind of mentorship, which illuminates the road to success.

We extend our heartfelt gratitude to our guide, **Mr. Roopesh Kumar B N**, for furnishing us with knowledge, leading us into the right direction, giving us his valuable time and providing guidance every step of the way, from the early stages of inception, to the completion of the project. This endeavour would not have seen the light of day and found itself at this stage without his unwavering encouragement and support.

We would also like to express our sincere gratitude to all the respected professors and faculty members of K S Institute of Technology, for their invaluable guidance and support.

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